

Estimating the cost of capital for solar PV projects using auction results

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ABSTRACT

The cost of capital (CoC) is an important parameter for accurately calculating power generation cost, particularly for capital-intensive renewables such as solar PV. However, data on CoC is sparse, which is an issue given large differences in CoC between countries and over time. The global trend towards competitive auctions for renewable energy deployment provides an opportunity to fill this gap. Here, we demonstrate how to combine auction price and project-level cost data to estimate the CoC for solar PV over time in nine countries, analysing 3'983 individual projects. Based on our results, we conclude that the CoC has fallen considerably across countries in all five continents analysed. These decreases were largely due to a reduction in premiums that investors demand for solar PV projects. We also find a strong decline in the variance of the data across time, pointing to better data quality and/or more homogenous project conditions. This trend is encouraging for future analyses, including potential CoC forecasting. However, given data quality issues and the amount of manual work required to address these, the approach should not be used as a standalone to estimate the CoC across countries.

1. Introduction

The rapid deployment of renewable energy (RE) technologies, such as solar photovoltaics (PV), is crucial to mitigate climate change (McCollum et al., 2018; IEA, 2021; IRENA, 2022b). Whereas lifetime costs for fossil fuel-based technologies are heavily influenced by fuel costs, lifetime costs for RE are dominated by upfront investment costs, which need to be financed (Schmidt, 2014). Consequently, the conditions on which RE developers can secure financing for their projects has a large effect on project cost and due to the disproportional importance for RE, also a large effect on the competitiveness of RE versus fossil fuel-based technologies (Schmidt et al., 2019). Another difference between fossil fuel-based and RE plants refers to the financing structure: while the former are mostly financed on the balance sheets of utilities using corporate finance structures (at least in OECD countries), the latter are to a much greater extent financed through project finance structures, i.e., non-recourse finance via special purpose vehicles for each individual project (Kann, 2009; Steffen, 2020). Unlike for corporate finance, the

financing cost for project finance structures are project-specific and hence harder to determine.¹

While the financing conditions of a renewable energy project include the cost of equity and debt, the loan tenor, the debt service coverage ratio and potentially other factors (Egli et al., 2018), most researchers and analysts operationalize financing conditions via the cost of capital (CoC) (Roth et al., 2022) or the private discount rate.² In its simplest form, the CoC is composed of the cost of equity that a project developer requires to take on the project risk, the cost of debt that a bank (or another debt provider) demands to lend money to the project, and the share of debt in the financing of the project. Combining these components, the CoC is the standard metric to represent financing conditions, yet we know remarkably little about the magnitude of CoC for RE projects globally (Steffen, 2020). Research has shown that RE CoC differs by country and technology and varies over time (Egli et al., 2019; Steffen and Waidelich, 2022). Capturing such differences and dynamic movements accurately is crucial to get a correct picture of the cost competitiveness of RE (Ameli et al., 2021; Polzin et al., 2021). The CoC is a key

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¹ While less common, there are also fossil fuel-based power plants being realized using project finance structures, e.g. in IPP schemes auctioned off in some countries. In principle, our method could be extended to study the cost of capital for such projects as well.

² Note that multiple models (additionally) use a social discount rate, which reflect the societal perspective on future costs and benefits. Here, we focus on the private rate, i.e., the perspective of an investor.

input variable in global, regional and national energy system models that provides advice to policymakers as to which generation technologies to support and deploy. The International Energy Agency (IEA) and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), the two most important international organisations in the field of energy system planning, have recently started using differentiated CoC in their models. As the energy modelling community is moving towards a more differentiated representation of CoC, reliable data inputs will become more important (Lonergan et al., 2023). Further, policymakers that aim for higher deployment of renewables can use lower CoC as a lever (Steffen and Waidelich, 2022; Dukan et al., 2023), but to this end first need to understand whether (and for which technologies) the CoC are too high (e.g., compared to best-in-class countries).

Yet, CoC figures are hard to obtain for at least two reasons. Firstly, many RE projects are realized in legally separated project-financed entities, for which financing information is not disclosed (Steffen, 2018). Relatedly, equity and debt investors may treat the cost of equity and debt respectively as confidential information to shield from competitors (Krupa and Harvey, 2017). Secondly, eliciting CoC is not trivial and there is a limited number of experts in a small number of financial institutions that are directly involved in financing RE projects. Obtaining reliable data therefore requires direct contact with these professionals, which is difficult and resource intensive to establish and even more difficult to maintain over time to keep estimates up to date. Consequently, academic and grey literature on the CoC for RE tends to be sparse and outdated (Steffen, 2020; Roth et al., 2022).

In this paper, we propose a way to address this shortage by making use of the fact that RE auctions have gained popularity among policymakers worldwide (IRENA, 2019b). Between 2010 and 2020, the number of solar PV projects awarded through competitive auctions and tracked by IRENA have increased more than 50-fold from 55 projects in 3 countries for 2010 to 3114 projects in 19 countries for 2020. Contrary to previous support schemes, which declared a fixed remuneration per kWh by law for a fixed period of time (e.g., feed-in tariff), reverse price auctions are competitive.³ The achieved final auction price is the outcome of a bidding price where each bidder needs to secure financing or uses assumptions about financing to place a bid (Anatolitis et al., 2022). Hence, the CoC in an auction is the result of a competitive market process. This fact can be used to reverse-engineer the CoC for auctioned projects to provide up to date CoC estimates for RE in a wide range of countries with additional project data (Steffen, 2020). While this approach is not new, it has previously been limited to a small number of auctions, which were analysed in detail (Apostoleris et al., 2018; Dobrotkova et al., 2018).

The contribution of this paper is twofold. First, we leverage a large IRENA dataset to apply the technique of reverse-engineering the CoC to a large number of solar PV projects in markets, including emerging economies, where eliciting CoC values is particularly challenging. The resulting dataset can be used as an additional source for input data in global or country-specific energy modelling (e.g., modelling the cost of decarbonizing electricity generation). Second, we critically examine the resulting CoC estimates to assess the usefulness of reverse-engineering CoC from auction results in improving the accurateness of energy models and thereby improving the quality of the analysis used for energy system policymaking.

³ Contrary to a classic auction where the highest bid wins, reverse price auctions seek to determine the lowest possible bid for a specified good or service. It is called reverse because the roles of buyer and seller are reversed and contrary to a classic auction it entails one buyer and several possible suppliers, i.e., bidders. It is often used in procurement.

2. Analysis

2.1. Approach

The starting point to reverse-engineer the CoC for auctioned projects is the price per kWh of electricity generated in a competitive Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) awarded through auctions. If these auctions are competitive, there should be no excess margins, such that the auction result (price per kWh) equal the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) of the bidder. There may be cases where auction prices are for example below a calculated LCOE if a project developer has a strategic interest in winning a bid and therefore is willing to take a financial hit for the long-term strategic value of entering a market. However, over time such dynamics should phase out as the market becomes competitive and debt plays a larger role in the financing (i.e., banks will not offer lower rates based on strategic considerations). As such, the assumption to equate PPA prices to the LCOE may not hold in every single auction but should hold on average when analysed in a large sample.

PPAs are often awarded through state-owned utilities or energy ministries and guarantee a fixed price, sometimes even indexed to inflation, for most of the lifetime of a power plant (typically 20 years, see Table A.2 in the Appendix). This long-term government revenue support mechanism can act as an indirect subsidy, lowering the PPA prices to below and associated CoCs below “market rates” absent government support. Further indirect subsidies include guaranteed grid access and sometimes preferential land lease rights. Also, potential subsidies that accrue to the project owner, such as the investment tax credit in the United States, are considered. In different words, we consider what could be referred to as “financial LCOE” (taking into account financing costs and subsidies), as compared to a “techno-economic LCOE” which simply uses a generic discount rate and disregards subsidies.

We use a simplified LCOE formula from NREL to estimate the CoC for each project (NREL, 2022). In Equation (1), i denotes a project, $CAPEX$ denotes the project-specific capital expenditure (this is the total installed cost, not overnight costs) per installed capacity (e.g. kW), $OPEX$ denotes the yearly operation & maintenance cost per installed capacity as per Table A.1 in the Appendix, and the Capacity Factor denotes the project-specific operation time corresponding to the amount of full load hours divided by 8760 h of the year.

$$PPA_i = LCOE_i = \frac{(CAPEX_i \times CRF_i) + OPEX}{8760 \times CapacityFactor_i} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1): Simplified LCOE equation (NREL, 2022).

CRF is the capital recovery factor, a ratio used to compute the present value of future PPA payments as given in Equation (2). The variable t denotes the total lifetime of the power plant in years, with is set to be equal to the term length of the PPA contract for each project i .

$$CRF_i = \frac{CoC_i \times (1 + CoC_i)^t}{(1 + CoC_i)^t - 1} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2): Simplified Capital Recovery Factor (CRF).

Once the project specific PPA price (assumed to be equal to the LCOE), the CAPEX, OPEX and PPA term length t is known, the CoC is solved for numerically using the solve function from the Python scipy library. As all data by IRENA are in real USD, the obtained CoC is real terms too. To obtain the nominal CoC, the average yearly US CPI inflation in the period 2011–2020, 1.73% was added to the real CoC. When calculating country averages for a given year, each project is weighted equally.

2.2. Scope of the analysis

Our analysis is limited to solar PV, the fastest growing RE technology in terms of capacity additions. In major markets, PV often features (a) lower CAPEX variations across projects and countries than other RE

technologies (IRENA, 2022a) and (b) generally experiences low O&M costs (Steffen et al., 2020). These characteristics reduce the potential error in calculating the CoC if project-level cost components are not fully reliable or unavailable. To cover a broad geographical area, 9 leading solar PV markets, covering 5 continents, were analysed that have conducted RE auctions. Collectively, these markets represent almost two thirds of the world solar PV deployment between 2011 and 2020 (IRENA, 2021). We analyse solar PV projects over 10 years, from 2011 to 2020.⁴

2.3. Data

2.3.1. Description of datasets

For our analysis, we leverage two proprietary datasets from IRENA, which have been maintained independently. The first database, hereafter called *cost database*, tracks key project-level data such as the capital expenditure and the capacity factor that allows IRENA to estimate the LCOE for given RE technology. The second database, hereafter called the *price database*, has been created by IRENA with the purpose to track the cleared prices in PPAs and the contractual details like term length and yearly inflation price adjustments (if any). For our 9 selected markets and time period (2011–2020), the raw cost database contained 3'811 projects with a cumulative capacity of 127.4 GW. The raw price database contained 6'409 projects with a capacity of 191.5 GW.

2.3.2. Merging of databases and estimating missing data

For computing the CoC of a project as outlined in Equation (1), the following five variables need to be known: (1) the cleared auction price, (2) the capital expenditure (CAPEX), (3) the operational expenditure (OPEX), (4) the capacity factor and (5) the duration of the PPA contract awarded.

The IRENA price database mainly tracks the auction price and the duration of the PPA contracts, and only occasionally simultaneously includes information on project-level CAPEX and capacity factor (76 of the 4'777 projects). The IRENA cost database was used to match as many auction projects as possible to the project-specific CAPEX and capacity factor data tracked through this second database. However, only a small subset of projects was both contained in the price and cost databases. For the majority of projects in the price database, the missing variables were estimated by using country-specific average CAPEX and capacity factor data of similar projects in the cost database. Project-specific data on operation and maintenance (OPEX) costs is extremely difficult to collect and is not tracked in either database. It is therefore added based on IRENA's general estimates for OECD and non-OECD countries in the years 2011–2020 (see Table A.1 in the Appendix).⁵ Lastly, we used publicly available data on term length to complement the data where term length data missing (see Table A.2 in the Appendix).

As the price and cost database had been maintained independently by IRENA, no database linkages existed for identical projects. To identify which projects were contained in both databases, a search function was developed to identify projects from the cost database with similar project name, size and installation year as a project from the price database. For each project in the price database, the search function suggested the most similar project in the cost database. Within the

⁴ Three factors motivate the selection of this period. First, we choose a period long enough to observe trends over time. Second, we are restricted by the application of RE auctions as a policy instrument (IRENA, 2019b). The start year of 2011 corresponds to the first year for which we have data available for at least three countries. Third, the selected period falls after the global financial crisis and ends before the COVID-19 crisis. Both global macroeconomic crises had a substantial impact on interest rates, which may distort observed trends over time.

⁵ For projects to be installed after 2020, a yearly 2.5% reduction in OPEX costs was assumed for each year after 2020.

search function, the string similarity of project names was computed by using the Levenshtein distance, implemented by the fuzzz function of the Python fuzzywuzzy library. Each suggested project was inspected manually to ensure accuracy, which yielded 177 matched projects, in addition to the 76 projects with full project-level data.

For projects that could not be matched using this semi-automated approach, missing project-level data (CAPEX and capacity factors) were estimated based on averaging these variables from projects in the *cost database* for the same country and presumed installation year. To reduce estimation errors, it was required that at least three projects exist in the cost database for a given country and installation year. The following steps were conducted to estimate the missing variables:

Step 1: If project-level data on CAPEX was unavailable, we used the country-average CAPEX from the cost database in the presumed installation year, which was typically two years after the PPA contract was awarded (see Table A2 in the Annex for lead times). Data was added for 2'580 projects via this procedure.

Step 2: Additionally, if the project-level data on capacity factors was also unavailable, we used the country-average in the presumed installation year. Data was added for 1'370 projects via this procedure.

Step 3: If calculating CAPEX or capacity factor was impossible because data in the presumed installation year was missing in the cost database, we used 3-year averages from the year prior to installation to the year after installation for both variables (1–3 years after the PPA award). Data was added for 221 projects via this procedure. After completing these steps, the sample database contained 4'424 projects.

For 2'115 projects in 2019 and 704 projects in 2020 (and installation in 2021 and 2022), no project-level CAPEX and capacity factor data was available in the cost database, as this had not been finalised in time for this project. To estimate the CAPEX in 2021 and 2022, we used projections made by IRENA in 2019 for the period 2020–2030 for G20 countries (IRENA, 2019a). For the capacity factor, 2020 data was used for estimating projects with presumed installation in 2021 and 2022 as it was assumed to stay approximately constant during this short time period.

For the United States, we adjust CAPEX values to account for the Federal Investment Tax Credit (ITC), which indirectly reduces CAPEX of a solar PV project (Krupa and Harvey, 2017). The ITC amounted to 30% for the period 2006–2019 and was reduced to 26% for 2020–2022 (U.S. Department of Energy, 2021). Accordingly, the CAPEX was reduced by these percentage amounts for projects in the United States in our database.

Finally, to further reduce the risk of outliers skewing the results, we remove projects where CAPEX or capacity factor values are beyond ± 2 standard deviations of the mean (by year for CAPEX, by country for capacity factor). This removes another 441 projects or 9.97% of our sample of 4'424 projects and results in a final database containing 3'983 projects with complete project-level data.

2.3.3. Final database

The resulting final dataset contains 3'983 solar PV projects with a total capacity of 98.6 GW for the selected 9 countries. Table 1 illustrates that the best coverage is reached for India (9 of 10 years). Most countries have introduced auctions only more recently, with the exception of South Africa, which started early but stopped temporarily in 2015. Over the entire time period, China and India auctioned off by far the highest capacity (52 GW and 30 GW respectively), however, the auctions in China mainly took place in 2019 alone. Finally, we observe that our sample provides a good global coverage with two countries from the Americas (Brazil and the US), two European countries (France and Germany), one African country (South Africa), two Middle Eastern countries (Jordan and UAE) and two Asian countries (China and India).

Table 1
Number of solar PV projects per country and year in final database ^a.

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total Projects	Total capacity (MW)
Brazil				14	59		12	20			105	2'975
China						1			1442	376	1'819	51'516
France		18		16	127	73		173	75		482	3'431
Germany					57	113	90		362	315	937	5'242
India	25	12	41	119	77	134	39	123	3		573	30'461
Jordan			15		1	1					17	382
South Africa	14	7	6		7						34	1'636
UAE						1	1				5	1'977
USA							9	5			14	995
Total	39	37	62	149	328	322	151	321	1883	691	3'983	98'616
Median project size (MW)	15.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	11.2	6.3	11.2	15.0	4.2	6.4	5.9	

^a Years are shaded if auctioned projects >0.

Table 2
Cost of capital per country and year in %.

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Brazil				6.9	13.5		7.6	0.6		
China						6.6			0.3	3.1
France		13.3		13.8	6.0	3.7		5.6	6.6	
Germany					5.0	2.9	0.2		2.1	1.5
India	9.2	11.5	8.1	12.6	11.6	10.4	8.3	11.0	9.2	
Jordan			16.2		6.9				8.1	
South Africa	21.4	7.8	9.1		7.9					
UAE						2.6	5.2			
USA							3.0	3.1		

3. Results

Successful auction bids are displayed in Fig. 1 as per the IRENA price database. Over time and across countries, the successful bids varied by a factor of 15 from 28.5 \$/MWh to 435 \$/MWh with the highest bid awarded in South Africa in 2011 and the lowest bid awarded in the United States of America in 2018 (note that Fig. 1 displays averages by year). Overall, our results show a clear trend of decreasing auction prices decreasing over time in all countries. Fig. 1 also shows a considerable variance across countries in the early years until roughly 2014 and increasingly converging auction prices afterwards. This is remarkable because the countries in our sample cover a very wide geography with different investment environments and institutional setups. For example, most auctions are in local currency (see Table A2 in the Annex) with substantial foreign exchange risks in countries such as Brazil, India or South Africa unless the investor is domestic. Relatedly, only few countries choose to peg the awarded price to inflation, which exposes investors to inflation risks that differ between countries.

Notwithstanding these differences in auction designs, we observe that in 2019 the average successful auction bids by country were in a relatively narrow range between 52.6 \$/MWh and 75.9 \$/MWh.

Results from the CoC reverse-engineering are shown in Fig. 2. Overall, the CoC has declined between 2011 and 2020, although with some exceptions. The highest estimated CoC values of above 20% appear in 2011 in South Africa and the lowest values in 2017 in Germany, at almost 0%. While a CoC estimate close to zero is questionable, other research confirms that the particular situation in Germany with a stable support regime and very low interest rates led to a very low CoC for renewables (Egli et al., 2018).

Similar to Germany, we calculated a very low CoC for Brazil in 2018 at 0.6%, which may be driven by the institutional setup. The national development bank of Brazil (BNDES) has been an important financier of RE like solar PV projects in Brazil during the last decade (Mazzucato and Penna, 2015). Consequently, the subsidized loans offered by BNDES may have driven down average returns. In 2018, BNDES reduced the already low interest rates on loans to solar projects from 1.7% to 0.9% p.

Fig. 1. Auction prices over time.

Fig. 2. Cost of capital over time.

a. (PV Magazine, 2018). Likewise, we estimate a very low CoC in 2019 in China. While data coverage on Chinese auctions in 2019 is very high with 1442 auction results (see Table 1), the quality of these data points is limited as no project-level CAPEX data was available and we used a Chinese average CAPEX to estimate the CoC (see step 1 in section 2.3.2). Furthermore, the precise auction conditions in China could not be fully clarified and the lack of data across time (only one project before 2016) makes it difficult to assess the data quality for China.

We conclude from this that auction results in Brazil and China are likely yielding less reliable CoC estimates and flag these countries in Figs. 2 and 4 accordingly. To address the uncertainty around the CoC estimates for Brazil and China, we show a sensitivity analysis on CAPEX and capacity factor in Fig. 3. These two inputs have the largest effect on the results as shown in Figure A3 in the Appendix. Fig. 3 shows that if CAPEX input data were 20% higher, this would reduce the CoC substantially, e.g., from 13.5% to 10.8% for Brazil in 2015 or from 3.1% to 1.4% for China in 2020. Conversely, a 20% higher capacity factor would have led to an increase in the CoC from 13.5% to 16.8% in Brazil in 2015, and from 3.1% to 5.5% for China in 2020.

To discuss country dynamics, we separate the data in two five-year periods in Fig. 4: 2011–2015 and 2016–2020. Table 3 shows summary statistics for auction prices and relevant input parameters as identified in Figure A3 (see Figure A1 for CAPEX evolution by country and Figure A2 for capacity factor evolution by country). It first shows that the standard deviation (SD) of all variables decreased considerably from the early to the later period. This indicates that country differences may be decreasing, resulting in more convergence and that data quality may be improving. The rapid and global cost decrease of solar PV is illustrated by the fact that the highest auction price in the recent period is roughly 26% below the mean in the early period and the highest CAPEX in the recent period is lower than the mean in the early period. Hence, countries across the board can benefit from low solar PV prices. Finally, there is some variance in PPA durations between 20 and 25 years in both periods with a trend towards 20 year term length in the late period (2016–2020).

Fig. 4 confirms the general pattern of declining CoC across countries

Fig. 4. Cost of capital estimates by country for early versus late period.

with relative declines between -9% for India and -66% for Germany from the early to the late period respectively. Absolute values are to be read with caution but correspond well to previous literature, which found values of 2.7% for Germany, 10.6% for India and 5.5% for Jordan in

Fig. 3. Cost of capital sensitivity analysis on CAPEX (A) and capacity factor (B) for Brazil and China.

Table 3
Key input variables in early versus late period.

	2011–2015				2016–2020			
	Mean	Min	Max	SD	Mean	Min	Max	SD
Auction price (real 2022 \$/MWh)	117.1	63.0	434.7	63.9	54.9	28.5	99.0	10.8
CAPEX (real 2022 \$/MW)	1569.0	827.0	5092.7	660.8	921.8	591.4	1425.2	174.2
Capacity factor (%)	17.4	12.5	29.0	3.6	12.9	10.3	24.0	2.2
PPA duration (years)	22.2	20.0	25.0	2.5	20.5	20.0	25.0	1.4

2017 (see Steffen, 2020 for an overview). To understand the risk premiums of PV projects, we split up the CoC into a base rate, using a 10-year US government bond yields plus country risk premiums (Damodaran, 2022), and a solar PV premium. The results show that the CoC declines are mainly due to lower solar PV risk premiums whereas base rates have stayed roughly constant. Risk premiums have declined substantially in all countries but India. When interpreting these figures, it is important to note that the base rate, i.e., the general interest rate, moves more than suggested in the aggregated time periods and potential upward swings can have a deteriorating effect on the CoC.

Fig. 4 also shows the two countries for which we deem interpreting results from reverse-calculating the CoC from auctions unreliable: Brazil and China. Both show negative solar PV premiums ranging from -2% to -2.7%, which means that we calculate a financing cost for solar PV that is below the financing cost for the government, i.e., a 10-year government bond. While there may be cases where this is plausible, it is unlikely for Brazil and China. One example would be an investment environment where government bonds yield a higher return than a solar PV plant with a private company offering a PPA because of a very bad public finance situation. Yet, the auctions analysed here are all government-backed, which rules out this argument. Rather, the reason of the negative risk premiums in these countries may be the strategic involvement of public finance institutions that offer subsidized credit in combination with a less transparent auction design (e.g., China), or a lack in data quality for other variables.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we aimed to test the usefulness of large N auction and project level data to reverse-engineer the CoC of solar PV projects in nine countries. Our results show the declining trend of CoC that has also been highlighted by studies using other approaches. As such, they support the general usefulness but also highlight the caveats of the large N approach. On the one hand, important data quality issues remain, and the data cleaning process (see Analysis) required a large amount of manual work. On the other hand, differences in auction policy designs between countries may complicate the interpretation of the findings. Our findings should always be read as results given the existing policy support frameworks. Hence, these results cannot inform us about the effects of different subsidies or policy frameworks but rather show the CoC that results from auction bids in the policy and economic environment at the time of the auction. For instance, subsidies beyond the guaranteed price of electricity in an auction can lead to a CoC estimate that is above what investors actually incur similar to a situation where the CAPEX of a project is lower than we assume (see Figure A3 in the Appendix). With increasing experience on the impacts of auction designs (Haelg, 2020; Dukan and Kitzing, 2021), one may also expect auction designs to converge across countries, which would make the reverse-engineering of CoC from auction results easier and more robust.

We identify five key insights related to the usefulness of estimating CoC from auction results to generate input data for energy modelling. First, the reliability of results differs by country (see Fig. 4) and as such the approach is most informative when paired with local context knowledge and it is likely less reliable for annual numbers compared to averages across years. Second, the variance in CoC estimates decreased substantially over the investigated period. Hence, the reliability of the

approach may increase in the future. Third, and as a consequence of the above, the approach should not be used stand-alone, but only in conjunction with and as a triangulation of other approaches to estimate the CoC. Fourth, determining under what circumstances the reliability is high or low requires a triangulation with other data sources, for which data on CoC should become more widely and publicly available. Fifth, the approach can point researchers to cases that are most relevant to understand better for policy advice. For example, understanding the constant risk premium in India (see Fig. 4) could be a task for a case study.

In conclusion, reverse-engineering the CoC from auctions cannot eliminate the need to elicit the CoC from experts but it can potentially help lower the frequency of costly and resource intense expert elicitation. While absolute CoC values derived from auction results must be cross-referenced and triangulated with other data sources, the widespread use of auctions and the increasing data availability enable the identification of time trends and country differences. Based on a triangulation with other data sources, these can help improve energy models and the basis for decision making in cases where seeking expert input may be too costly or too time consuming. Such improvements are especially important for developing and emerging countries, which are disproportionately affected from the use of uniform CoC leading to an underestimation of investment needs for the transition in these countries (Ameli et al., 2021).

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Florian Egli: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Nikolai Orgland:** Methodology, Data and Analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Michael Taylor:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Tobias S. Schmidt:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Bjarne Steffen:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix

Fig. A.1. Mean CAPEX over time by country

Fig. A.2. Mean capacity factor over time by country

Fig. A.3. Sensitivity analysis of the CoC for a reference project with ± 1 SD (top) and ± 25% variation (bottom)

Table A.1
OPEX inputs (IRENA, 2022a)

Year	OECD 2020 USD/kW/year	Non-OECD 2020 USD/kW/year
2010	26.2	24.7
2011	23.2	22.7
2012	22.6	17.6
2013	22.1	14.8
2014	21.6	13.2
2015	20.9	12.0
2016	20.4	10.9
2017	20.8	10.5
2018	19.4	10.0
2019	18.5	9.6
2020	17.6	9.3

Table A.2
Key auction characteristics (authors compilation)

Country	Realisation period (years)	PPA length (years)	PPA currency	PPA inflation indexation	Grid connection paid by ⁷	Land lease paid by
Brazil	2	20	Local	Yes (Local CPI)	PD	PD
China	0.5	20	Local	No	PD	PD
France	2	20	Local	Yes (industrial prod. and wage inflation)	PD	PD
Germany	2	20	Local	No	PD	PD
India	2	25	Local	No	PD/Public	PD/Public
Jordan	2	20	Local pegged to USD	No	Public	PD
South Africa	2	20	Local	Yes (indexed to the rate of inflation)	Public	PD

(continued on next page)

Table A.2 (continued)

Country	Realisation period (years)	PPA length (years)	PPA currency	PPA inflation indexation	Grid connection paid by ⁷	Land lease paid by
United Arab Emirates	2	25	Local	No	Public	PD/Public
USA	2	20	Local	No	PD	PD

⁷ PD = Project developer.

Table A.3

Mean CAPEX per country and year in USD per kW

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Brazil				1975	1342		820	1070		
China						1231			1028	738
France		2586		1543	1493	1323		930	884	
Germany					1355	1357	972		774	718
India	2584	1848	2028	1085	987	884	760	595	862	
Jordan			2734		1207				1126	
South Africa	3896	3648	2208		1352					
UAE						1181	781			
USA							1200	797		

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